

MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF RATS KIDNEYS UNDER EXPOSURE TO ETHYL ALCOHOL IN THE AGE ASPECT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10147471>

Relevance: According to the World Health Organization, in 2016 there were over 180 million alcoholics in the world, and the prevalence rate was 2%. And at the same time, the “alcohol” situation in developed countries is different. M. A. Schuckit characterizes the situation in the United States by 2015 as follows: 90% of Americans drink alcohol during their lives, 60-70% drink alcohol systematically, more than 40% have alcohol-related problems, 20% of men and 10% of women abuse alcohol, have alcohol dependence, that is, 10% of men and 3.5% of women suffer from alcoholism. Opinions on the issue of kidney damage during acute alcohol intoxication are polar. Some authors do not consider the kidneys to be the target organs of ethanol, others consider ethyl alcohol to be the etiological factor in their damage and even identify alcoholic nephropathy, confirming it with clinical and experimental studies.

Purpose of the study: study of the morphometric parameters of the kidneys of white laboratory rats of various ages when exposed to ethyl alcohol.

Materials and research methods: We selected 128 mature outbred white rats of both sexes, whose age ranged from 3 to 12 months, weighing 200 g, raised under standard vivarium conditions for experimental scientific research. Laboratory animals were kept in the vivarium of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. The rats were kept in special rooms (room temperature 20-24°C, humidity 60%, illumination 12 hours) in accordance with the requirements for experimental animals.

Conclusion: When comparing the results of the experiment, it was revealed that in all age groups the microanatomical parameters of the nephron of the kidneys increase. At 12 months of postnatal development in rats, the greatest increase in the diameter of the glomerulus, the thickness of the Shumlyansky-Bowman capsule and the collecting ducts of the kidneys was 19.8%, 29.1%, 25.9%, respectively. The greatest increase in the diameter of the primary and secondary convolutions of the nephron of the kidneys was detected at 3 months of age - 33.6, 37.3%, respectively.

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